

BEYOND CONVENIENCE: HOW INSTANT GRATIFICATION AND ECONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS SHAPE QUICK COMMERCE ADOPTION

Maya Vimal Pandey*

Doctoral Research Fellow, Birla Institute of Management Technology,
Knowledge Park 2, Bimtech Road, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

*Corresponding Author Email: maya.pandey_fpm20@bimtech.ac.in;

ORCID: 0000-0002-4085-3046

Ashish Awasthi

Research Fellow, Birla Institute of Management Technology,
Knowledge Park 2, Bimtech Road, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Email: ashish.awasthi_fpm22@bimtech.ac.in; ORCID: 0000-0001-5954-0368

SM Fatah Uddin

Area Head, Marketing and Retail, Birla Institute of Management Technology,
Knowledge Park 2, Bimtech Road, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Email: sm.fatahuddin@bimtech.ac.in; ORCID: 0000-0002-3088-7963

Abstract

Quick commerce (Q-commerce) has emerged as a rapidly growing, hyper local, ultra-fast retail format. Limited academic research on quick commerce is restricted to operational, logistics and service quality aspects, leaving room for consumer behaviour studies. Identifying and addressing this gap, the present study applies Theory of Planned Behaviour to explore the factors impacting the adoption of Q-commerce. The framework of the study positions utilitarian drivers such as *convenience* and *time saving orientation* as antecedents of *attitude*. Further, *perceived behavioural control* is proposed to influence both *attitude* and *intention* to adopt Q-commerce. Additionally, *instant gratification orientation* and price saving orientation are positioned as moderators, influencing the relationship between attitude and intention. Data from 383 consumers were analysed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) on SmartPLS 4.0. Findings of the study suggest that while convenience, time saving orientation and perceived behavioural control significantly influence attitude toward intention for Q-commerce adoption. Out of the two moderators, only instant gratification orientation significantly influences the relationship between attitude and intention. Moderating effect of price saving orientation is not supported. Intention to adopt Q-commerce is significantly influenced by attitude and perceived behavioural control. The model demonstrates significant explanatory power. The study contributes to the consumer behaviour literature by integrating utilitarian and psychological drivers within TPB framework, offering actionable insights to retail platform managers seeking consumer adoption.

Keywords: *Theory of Planned Behaviour, Quick Commerce, Behavioural Intentions, Instant Gratification, Price Saving, Consumer Adoption.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Quick Commerce sector in India, presently valued at 3.35 Billion USD is estimated to cross 9 Billion USD by 2029 (The Economic Times Online, 2025). With existing companies aiming rapid growth into tier-2 and tier-3 cities, beyond the metros, and new ones ready to join the market, the industry, though at a nascent stage, is poised for a rapid growth (Shrivastav, 2025). The speed and convenience are the key differentiators of this retail format and thus, Yang et al. (2024) have defined Q-commerce as the variant of e-commerce where the product is delivered within 15 minutes to the consumer, once the order is placed.

While normal e-commerce takes a couple of days to deliver the product, Q-commerce does the same in few minutes. Q-commerce prioritises speed, convenience and instant gratification (Yang et al., 2024) leveraging the concept of dark stores which are micro-fulfilment centres located within densely populated urban areas. Through an app-based service, Q-commerce enables a large number of consumers to get the desired products quickly. Thus, it thrives on digitalization and automation. Aiming to deliver seamless, tech-enabled service experience to the consumers (Gund and Daniel, 2023), Q-commerce is in a high growth trajectory specifically in emerging economies like India (Red Seer, 2024).

Post Covid-19, consumers' shopping preference has undergone a profound transformation with more, specifically the younger consumers preferring online shopping rather than visiting physical stores (Market Brew, 2024b). This indicates a growing trend in Q-commerce consumer base with the number slated to cross 60 million by 2029 Statista (2024). Q-commerce is being called as the next generation retail format, as it offers superfast delivery at ultra-convenience to the consumers along with a plethora of product choices i.e. wide assortment.

Although a large consumer base has still not adopted Q-commerce due to the reasons like poor packaging, low digital literacy, dark side of 'dark stores' (mini warehouses for quick commerce) and poor product quality (NDTV, 2025), the consumer behaviour regarding Q-commerce warrants a deeper, research based examination, specifically in the context of emerging economies like India, where Q-commerce adoption is on the rise (Kapoor et al., 2023; Harter et al., 2025; Rai et al., 2023).

While e-commerce, the predecessor to Q-commerce has been widely studied in academics from different perspectives (AlGhamdi et al., 2013; Giang et al., 2025), limited research is available on Q-commerce. Hence, the broad objective of this study is to examine the adoption of Q-commerce in an emerging economy like India.

The existing research on Q-commerce can be categorised into two groups – operational and behavioural. While the operational research in the domain of Q-commerce largely investigates logistics optimization, routing and dark store operations (Ma et al., 2025; Lee et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2024), behavioural research focuses on examination of Q-commerce service quality, consumer adoption of Q-commerce and the impact of delivery time on the decision to repurchase products using Q-commerce (Deepthi and Bansal, 2023; Harter et al., 2025;). Being a mobile-app based service, Q-commerce has been investigated through the perspectives of technology adoption theories such as Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Thapa, 2025; Giang et al., 2025), although the coverage of behavioural and psychological theories such as Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) is low in this domain. Addressing the above gap, the present study adopts a TPB perspective to study the adoption of Quick Commerce in India.

The following are the research questions (RQs) that the study addresses:

RQ1: What utilitarian factors shape the attitude of consumers towards Q-commerce adoption?

RQ2: How do attitude and perceived behavioural control drive Q-commerce adoption intentions?

RQ3: How do instant gratification orientation and price-saving orientation act in the translation of attitude to behavioural intention with regards to Q-commerce adoption?

To address these RQs, the study empirically examines an extended Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) framework in the context of quick commerce. The research framework includes key utilitarian drivers such as convenience, time-saving orientation, along with perceived behavioural control as antecedents of consumers' attitudes toward adoption, while retaining perceived behavioural control as a direct predictor of behavioural intention. Further, addressing the growing relevance of immediacy in digital consumption, this study introduces instant gratification orientation as a moderating construct influencing the relationship between attitude and behavioural intention. Additionally, price saving orientation is proposed to moderate the relationship between attitude and intention. By integrating rational decision-making with the tendency of seeking immediate reward and securing economic benefits, the study provides a more nuanced understanding of consumer adoption behaviour in quick commerce and extends the explanatory power of TPB in emerging, time-sensitive consumption contexts.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The limited extant literature on Q-commerce highlights its rapid emergence as a distinct retail paradigm marked with hyper-local ultra-fast delivery. The existing studies on quick commerce can be divided into two categories – logistics and operations research and consumer research. While the first category of studies tries to answer the 'how' of Q-commerce, the second category of studies attempt answering the 'why' of Q-commerce. The 'how' studies focus on dark store operations, routing optimization and drone based delivery to enhance operational efficiency and ensure last mile logistics (Ma et al., 2025; Pachayappan, 2023). The studies in this category also focus on development of mathematical models to improve order fulfillment in Q-commerce (Raj et al., 2024). Further, studies have examined the role of dark stores as enablers of fulfillment under the conditions of demand uncertainty (Lee et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2024). Limited studies in this category have also focused on the overall viability of the Q-commerce business model within urban retail ecosystems (Guru et al., 2023). Collectively, though limited in number, these studies provide valuable information on infrastructural, technological and logistical aspects of Q-commerce.

The studies addressing the 'why' of Q-commerce examine service quality, consumer adoption and service outcomes. Several studies have focused on consumer's trust and policy related factors that influence trust, role of service quality in Q-commerce consumer satisfaction (Al Mu'ani et al., 2024). Using Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), studies have attempted to explain user adoption of Q-commerce (Deepthi & Bansal, 2023). A few studies have also focused on delivery speed and its influence on consumers repurchase decision, highlighting the pivotal role of speed in consumer satisfaction with Q-commerce (Harter et al., 2025). Service experiences of Q-commerce consumers

have also been studied using methods such as SEM (Kapoor et al., 2023). The extant literature also includes a limited number of case-based studies highlighting the evolution of Q-commerce as a distinct and influential retail format and the competitive landscape of the industry in the context of an emerging economy like India (Sanghi et al., 2024). Further, the 'why' literature has also focused on sustainability and circular economy practices in Q-commerce sector (Chavhan & Dutta, 2025) alongside product specific studies such as delivery of instant food through Q-commerce (Sahu et al., 2025).

Despite the limited but growing number of studies on Q-commerce, the existing literature remains anchored in technology-oriented theories like TAM, emphasizing on attributes such as perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. While these theoretical perspectives offer valuable insights, they often take a narrow view of consumer decision making dynamics ignoring context sensitive factors in a time focused phenomenon such as Q-commerce. In contrast, Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) by considering evaluative constructs like attitude, perceived behavioural control and social influence, offer a more nuanced explanation of Q-commerce. Prior literature on e-commerce has utilized TPB to explain digital purchase and digital adoption intentions (Pavlou & Fygenson, 2006; George, 2004). However, in the context of Q-commerce, TPB framework remains under-explored. Prior literature on Q-commerce has not utilized TPB to account for Q-commerce specific factors like time saving based decision making, hyper-convenience, price saving orientation and immediate gratification, suggesting a need for theoretical extension. Further, while prior studies have examined utilitarian drivers such as convenience and price, limited attention has been paid to how consumer-level orientations, both psychological (instant gratification) and economic (price-saving orientation), interact with attitude to shape behavioural intentions in Q-commerce contexts.

Q-commerce is a consumption context rooted in immediacy. Despite this, the extant literature has not specifically addressed psychological constructs that capture the immediacy-oriented nature of Q-commerce. The concept of instant gratification, originating in consumer psychology literature, reflects the tendency of an individual to expect immediate rewards rather than delayed outcomes (Mischel et al., 1989; Loewenstein, 1996). This tendency of instant gratification gets boosted further in digital consumption contexts which were designed to reduce waiting time, enabling real time fulfillment (Dholakia, 2000). Q-commerce platforms directly cater to this tendency of instant satisfaction; however, the existing studies have largely ignored this important psychological construct while addressing speed and convenience as the major service attributes. This is a critical research gap as the instant gratification orientation may significantly influence the translation of favourable consumer attitude into intention to use Q-commerce. Moreover, while prior studies have, in a limited way, addressed utilitarian constructs like time saving and price saving, their integration with TPB alongside instant gratification orientation is still under-explored. In addition, it remains unclear whether immediacy-driven tendencies or economic considerations such as price-saving orientation play a more decisive role in influencing the attitude–intention relationship in Q-commerce.

Addressing these gaps, the present study incorporates key utilitarian drivers – convenience and time saving orientation as the antecedent of attitude while examining the influence of perceived behavioural control on attitude as well as intention to adopt Q-commerce. Further, the study introduces instant gratification orientation and price saving orientation as moderating constructs

influencing the relationship between attitude and intention to adopt Q-commerce. By doing so, the study deviates from traditional adoption frameworks and offers a more nuanced understanding of Q-commerce including both context-specific, price oriented and immediacy-oriented constructs, contributing to both theory and practice.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Adopting Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) as the foundational theory, the study explains the adoption of Q-commerce among Indian consumers. TPB posits that behavioural intention is the most immediate predictor of behaviour and is shaped by factors such as attitude and perceived behavioural control. Attitude reflects the overall disposition of an individual; it is an evaluative construct whose outcome is either favourable or unfavourable. Perceived behavioural control on the other hand represents the perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour. Together, the two constructs significantly explain the variance in behavioural intention in a wide range of contexts including digital purchasing ((Ajzen, 1991; Bosnjak et al., 2020). TPB has been successfully extended to e-commerce adoption by prior studies (Pavlou & Fygenson, 2006). Based on these insights, the present study refines TPB in the context of Q-commerce by incorporating context-specific antecedents and relevant moderating mechanisms.

Utilitarian drivers and attitude

Q-commerce is a consumption context driven by utility where convenience, speed and functional benefits substantially shape consumers decisions. Convenience (CON) is the central driver of Q-commerce including effort saving, ease of using the platform etc. in the digital consumption context. Convenience has been linked directly with formation of favourable attitude through the reduction of physical and cognitive effort. Similarly, time saving orientation (TSO) plays a critical role in formation of attitude of the consumers' towards Q-commerce. Consumers with stronger time saving orientation are more likely to have a positive and favourable attitude towards Q-commerce. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H₁: Convenience (CON) positively influences attitude towards Q-commerce adoption.

H₂: Time saving orientation (TSO) positively influences attitude towards Q-commerce adoption.

Role of perceived behavioural control

Perceived behavioural control (PBC) is a reflection of an individual's perception regarding the performance of a behaviour given the skills, resources and facilitating conditions (Ajzen, 1991). PBC may include factors such as the ease of a particular app usage and ability to make payments online. While traditionally, PBC influences behavioural intentions, but the emerging research suggests that PBC may influence attitude as well, specifically in digital consumption context where perceived ease significantly shapes the overall service perception. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H₃: Perceived behavioural control (PBC) positively influences consumers' attitude toward Q-commerce adoption.

H₄: Perceived behavioural control (PBC) positively influences consumers' behavioural intention toward the adoption of Q-commerce.

Attitude and Behavioural intention to adopt quick commerce

A positive and favourable attitude (ATT) towards Q-commerce, driven by utilitarian drivers and perceived behavioural control is expected to translate into stronger behavioural intention to adopt Q-commerce. Prior studies have consistently emphasized on the predictive role of attitude towards behavioural intention (Ajzen, 1991; Bosnjak et al., 2020). Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Attitude towards Q-commerce adoption (ATT) positively influences consumers' behavioural intention toward the adoption of Q-commerce.

Moderating role of instant gratification orientation

Q-commerce operates in an environment of immediate fulfilment and instant satisfaction. The concept of instant gratification posits that consumers prefer immediate rewards compared to delayed outcomes (Mischel et al., 1989; Loewenstein, 1996). Digital platforms are designed to cater to the consumers, offering them real time deliveries and immediate fulfilment (Dholakia, 2000). In the Q-commerce context, consumers with high instant gratification orientation are expected to act on positive attitude without delay. Therefore, instant gratification orientation (IGO) is expected to strengthen the relationship between attitude toward Q-commerce adoption and intention to adoption Q-commerce. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: Instant gratification orientation (IGO) positively moderates the relationship between attitude and behavioural intention in Q-commerce adoption.

Moderating role of price saving orientation

Besides utilitarian and psychological drivers, economic considerations also play an important role in consumers' purchase decisions. Price saving orientation reflects the tendency of consumers to prioritize purchase on the basis of price discounts, cost savings and other such monetary rewards in their purchase decisions. In Q-commerce, convenience arrives at a premium, thus, consumers with strong price saving orientation may evaluate cost-benefit trade-off more critically. Thus, price saving orientation may influence the translation of attitude into intention, depending on the extent to which economic value is prioritized by the consumers. Price saving orientation, therefore, is proposed as a boundary condition in the study. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed

H7: Price-saving orientation (PSO) moderates the relationship between attitude towards Q-commerce and behavioural intention to adopt Q-commerce.

Overall, the proposed conceptual framework refines TBP by integrating utilitarian drivers (convenience and time saving orientation) as the antecedents of attitude, while placing perceived behavioural control as a predictor of both attitude as well as intention to adopt Q-commerce. Additionally, instant gratification orientation and price saving orientation are proposed as moderators, influencing the relationship between attitude and intention to adopt Q-commerce. The model captures the interplay between economic consideration and psychological immediacy, providing a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of Q-commerce as a time-sensitive and value-driven consumption phenomenon. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework (Based on Theory of Planned Behaviour, Ajzen, 1991)

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional research design. Quantitative design was considered appropriate as the study seeks to empirically examine the proposed relationship between latent construct and assess the predictive capability of the research model. Specifically, the study seeks to understand how utilitarian drivers influence attitude towards Q-commerce, how attitude and perceived behavioural control influence intention to adopt Q-commerce and how immediacy and price orientations, as moderators, influence the relationship between attitude and intention to adopt Q-commerce. Given the predictive orientation, inclusion of latent constructs from outside TPB and presence of multiple moderators as well as mediator (attitude), PLS-SEM was considered appropriate method to analyse data. PLS-SEM is particularly suitable when the objective is to know the predictive capability of a complex model, along with estimation of direct, indirect and moderating effects (Hair et al., 2022). Additionally, PLS-SEM allows analysis of complex models without imposing normality restrictions. It is widely used in consumer behaviour and technology adoption studies.

Sampling and data collection

Purposive sampling design was employed for data collection. It is widely accepted and used in consumer research as it enables the researchers to collect data from respondents who qualify relevant criteria for the research. In case of this study, the criterion was familiarity (not necessarily usage) with Q-commerce apps as the study's objective was to study intention and not actual behaviour. Through a structured questionnaire, the study collected data from respondents who were familiar with and were potential users of Q-commerce apps operating in India such as Zepto, Blinkit Swiggy Instamart and related platforms. India represent ideal empirical setting for this study

due to rising penetration of smart phones, increasing digital literacy and increasing preference of consumers to adopt retailing formats defined by convenience. Data was collected from major metropolitan cities of India having Q-commerce operations.

Screening questions in the beginning of the questionnaire ensured inclusion of only relevant respondents. Respondents lacking Q-commerce awareness were kept out of the data collection process. After data cleaning, 383 valid responses were obtained which were retained for data analysis. This sample size is considered adequate based on statistical power considerations and common recommendations (1:10 rule), providing sufficient robustness for bootstrapping procedure for statistical significance testing (Hair et al., 2022). Table 1 shows the respondents' profile.

Table 1: Respondents' profile (Source: authors' own work)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	216	56.4
	Female	167	43.6
Age Group	18-25 years	148	38.6
	26-35 years	137	35.8
	36-45 years	66	17.2
	Above 45 years	32	8.4
Education	Undergraduate	129	33.7
	Postgraduate	181	47.3
	Doctoral / Professional	42	11.0
	Other	31	8.1
Occupation	Student	96	25.1
	Salaried Employee	187	48.8
	Self-employed / Business	54	14.1
	Homemaker	21	5.5
	Other	25	6.5
Monthly Income	Below ₹25,000	92	24.0
	₹25,001-₹50,000	128	33.4
	₹50,001-₹75,000	93	24.3
	Above ₹75,000	70	18.3
Quick Commerce Usage Frequency	Daily	74	19.3
	Weekly	169	44.1
	Monthly	91	23.8
	Rarely	49	12.8
Total - 383			

Measurement Instrument

A structured questionnaire was developed using multi-item pre-established scales adopted from prior research and contextualized for the present study. This is a widely accepted practice in consumer behaviour research. All the constructs were operationalized as reflective constructs. The questionnaire consisted of a demographic section where demographic data of the respondents was collected. The main section of the questionnaire consisted items related to constructs, on which the data was collected from the respondents on a 5-point Likert scale. Table 2 shows the constructs and corresponding scale items included in the questionnaire.

Table 2: Constructs and corresponding scale items (Source: prior studies)

Construct	Indicative Scale Items*	Key Source(s)
Convenience (CON)	CON1: Using quick commerce apps saves me effort while shopping. CON2: Quick commerce apps make shopping more convenient. CON3: It is easy to purchase products through quick commerce apps. CON4: Quick commerce apps enables hassle-free shopping. CON5: Using quick commerce apps reduces the inconvenience of visiting physical stores.	Berry et al. (2002)
Time-Saving Orientation (TSO)	TSO1: Saving time is important to me while shopping. TSO2: I prefer shopping options that reduce time spent on purchasing. TSO3: I value services that help me complete shopping quickly. TSO4: I choose retail formats that minimize shopping time.	Seiders et al. (2007); Konoş et al. (2008)
Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC)	PBC1: I have the ability to use quick commerce apps. PBC2: Using quick commerce apps is within my control. PBC3: I have the resources and knowledge required to use quick commerce services.	Ajzen (1991); Taylor & Todd (1995)
Attitude (ATT)	ATT1: Using quick commerce apps is a good idea. ATT2: Using quick commerce apps is beneficial for me. ATT3: Using quick commerce apps is a wise choice. ATT4: I have a favourable opinion about using quick commerce apps.	Ajzen (1991); Pavlou & Fygenson (2006)
Behavioural Intention (INT)	INT1: I intend to use quick commerce apps in the future. INT2: I will frequently use quick commerce apps whenever needed. INT3: I am likely to choose quick commerce apps for future purchases.	Ajzen (1991); Venkatesh et al. (2003)
Instant Gratification Orientation (IGO)	IGO1: I prefer getting products immediately rather than waiting. IGO2: I like services that satisfy my needs instantly. IGO3: I am attracted to options that provide immediate fulfilment.	Loewenstein (1996); Dholakia (2000)
Price-Saving Orientation (PSO)	PSO1: I prefer shopping options that help me save money. PSO2: I compare prices before making purchase decisions. PSO3: Discounts and savings strongly influence my shopping choices.	Lichtenstein et al. (1993); Wakefield & Inman (2003)

All measurement items were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. Prior to full-scale data collection, the instrument was reviewed for the clarity of wording, contextual relevance, and face validity.

Data analysis techniques

Data was analysed using SmartPLS 4.0 following the established guidelines of PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2022). The analysis included two stages- the assessment of measurement model and the assessment of structural model.

The measurement model was assessed for indicator reliability, internal consistency reliability; construct reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity. Indicator reliability was examined through outer loading values with 0.7 as the minimum acceptable threshold. Internal consistency reliability was assessed by observing Cronbach Alpha (α) value with 0.7 as the minimum acceptable value, construct reliability was examined through the values of composite reliability (CR) with 0.7 as the minimum acceptable benchmark. Convergent validity was assessed through Average Variance Extracted (AVE) with 0.5 as the acceptable minimum threshold. Discriminant validity was examined through Fornell-Larcker criterion, which is widely followed in consumer behaviour research. Multicollinearity issues among indicators were examined using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values (Hair et al., 2022).

After assessing the measurement model, the structural model was assessed by examining the values of path coefficients, coefficient of determination (R^2), effect sizes (f^2), predictive relevance (Q^2), and significance of hypothesized relationships.

Additionally, moderation effects were examined through path coefficient and mediation effects were examined through specific indirect path parameters. The significance of direct, indirect, and moderating effects was tested using a bootstrapping procedure with resampling. Bootstrapping provides robust estimates of standard errors, t-values, and confidence intervals without assuming normal data distribution (Hair et al., 2022).

Ethical considerations

The study followed ethical guidelines for quantitative survey research. Participation in the survey was voluntary and anonymous. The respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and they were free to withdraw from the survey at any time without consequences. No personal identification information was collected from the respondents. The data was used only for academic purpose. The methodology adopted in the study followed established guidelines for PLS-SEM best practices thereby ensuring rigor and transparency. Common method bias was assessed using Harman's single-factor test with first factor accounting for less than 50% of the total variance, indicating that common method bias was not a serious concern (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Data analysis (PLS-SEM) was conducted using SmartPLS 4.0 on 383 responses finally retained. The respondents belonged to the metropolitan cities where Q-commerce services are highly active, making them a suitable sample for study on Q-commerce adoption. Most of the respondents were young urban consumers. Prior studies show that younger age groups exhibit a higher tendency to adopt digital retail format, making this group a highly suited cohort for the study (Kapoor et al., 2023; Harter et al., 2025).

The section below presents the results of data analysis and related findings. Following the PLS-SEM guidelines (Hair et al., 2022), assessment of measurement model was conducted followed by assessment of structural model. Subsequently moderation, mediation and predictive capability of the model were evaluated.

Assessment of measurement model

All the constructs in the conceptual framework were specified as reflective constructs. Indicator reliability was assessed through outer loadings. Following the recommendation of PLS-SEM guidelines, 0.70 was considered the minimum acceptable threshold for reliability. All indicators loaded significantly on their respective constructs with loadings value ranging from 0.730 to 0.886, suggesting that all the constructs were adequately represented by their respective indicators (items).

Cronbach's alpha (α) and Composite Reliability (CR) were examined to assess internal consistency reliability. While α value ranged from 0.718 to 0.865, CR values ranged from 0.843 to 0.902, both exceeding the minimum acceptable criterion of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2022), indicating adequate internal consistency reliability. Item loadings and construct reliability values (α and CR) are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Measurement items loading and construct reliability

Dimensions	Items	loadings	α	CR
Convenience	CON1	0.757	0.865	0.902
	CON2	0.828		
	CON3	0.810		
	CON4	0.814		
	CON5	0.815		
Time Saving Orientation	TSO1	0.827	0.847	0.897
	TSO2	0.863		
	TSO3	0.838		
	TSO4	0.784		
Perceived Behavioural Control	PBC1	0.886	0.773	0.868
	PBC2	0.738		
	PBC3	0.856		
Attitude towards Quick Commerce	ATT1	0.851	0.849	0.898
	ATT2	0.852		
	ATT3	0.816		
	ATT4	0.799		
Intention to adopt Quick Commerce	INT1	0.787	0.795	0.879
	INT2	0.852		
	INT3	0.881		
Instant Gratification Orientation	IGO1	0.796	0.750	0.857
	IGO2	0.837		
	IGO3	0.816		
Price Saving Orientation	PSO1	0.825	0.718	0.843
	PSO2	0.730		
	PSO3	0.843		

Convergent validity was examined through the values of Average Variance Extracted (AVE), which ranged from 0.642 to 0.708, exceeding the minimum acceptable threshold of 0.50, indicating adequate convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Fornell-Larcker criterion was used to evaluate the discriminant validity. It was observed that the square root of AVE for each construct exceeded its inter-construct correlations. Therefore, Fornell-Larcker criterion was fully satisfied, indicating that all the constructs were conceptually and empirically distinct from each other (Henseler et al., 2015). AVE and Fornell-Larcker criterion values are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Validity results (AVE and Fornell-Larcker criterion)

	AVE	ATT	CON	IGO	INT	PBC	PSO	TSO
ATT	0.688	0.829						
CON	0.648	0.608	0.805					
IGO	0.666	0.507	0.671	0.816				
INT	0.708	0.733	0.586	0.482	0.841			
PBC	0.687	0.525	0.567	0.661	0.545	0.829		
PSO	0.642	0.627	0.612	0.607	0.601	0.584	0.801	
TSO	0.687	0.612	0.792	0.693	0.609	0.580	0.673	0.829

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for both outer and inner models were below the recommended cut-off values, less than 3.3, indicating the absence of multicollinearity concerns (Hair et al., 2022). Overall, the assessment of measurement model was satisfactory with all the parameters of reliability and validity in acceptable range as per the latest PLS-SEM guidelines (Hair

et al., 2022).

Assessment of structural model

Following the confirmation of the reliability and the validity of the measurement model, the assessment of the structural model was done through the procedure of bootstrapping, as recommended by Hair et al. (2022), as per established guidelines of PLS-SEM. While coefficient of determination, i.e., R^2 for attitude towards Q-commerce (ATT) was found 0.44, R^2 for intention to adopt quick commerce (INT) was found 0.594, indicating strong explanatory power of the model, specifically in case of behavioural intention, the focal construct of the study, where the given model is able to explain almost 60% of the variance (Hair et al., 2022). It can be observed from Table 5a that convenience (CON) significantly influences attitude ($\beta = 0.270$, $t = 3.951$, $p < 0.001$). Therefore H_1 is supported. This finding reinforces prior studies emphasizing convenience as the fundamental value proposition in the online consumption (Berry et al., 2002; Jiang et al., 2013). Similarly, time-saving orientation (TSO) positively influences attitude ($\beta = 0.275$, $t = 3.827$, $p < 0.001$), supporting H_2 and indicating that consumers who value time are more likely to develop favourable disposition towards Q-commerce adoption. Perceived behavioural control (PBC) significantly influenced attitude ($\beta = 0.212$, $t = 3.615$, $p < 0.001$), supporting H_3 , and also significantly influences behavioural intention ($\beta = 0.170$, $t = 3.341$, $p = 0.001$), supporting H_4 . This result aligns with prior TPB literature, which emphasizes that consumers' perceptions of control, resources, and capability enhance behavioural intention (Ajzen, 1991; Pavlou & Fygenson, 2006). Further, attitude (ATT) shows a strong positive influence on intention to adopt Q-commerce ($\beta = 0.535$, $t = 9.443$, $p < 0.001$), supporting H_5 . This was the strongest structural path in the model which reinforced the central role of attitude as a predictor of adoption intention in TPB-based studies (Bosnjak et al., 2020). The results of structural model analysis and hypothesis examination are shown in Table 5a & 5b., and the Structural model is shown in Figure 2.

Table 5a: Structural model results and hypothesis testing

Relationship	Hypothesis	f^2	β	SD	T statistics	P values	Results
ATT -> INT	H_5	0.372	0.535	0.057	9.443	0.000	Supported
CON -> ATT	H_1	0.046	0.270	0.068	3.951	0.000	Supported
PBC -> ATT	H_3	0.051	0.212	0.059	3.615	0.000	Supported
PBC -> INT	H_4	0.035	0.170	0.051	3.341	0.001	Supported
TSO -> ATT	H_2	0.047	0.275	0.072	3.827	0.000	Supported
IGO x ATT -> INT	H_6	0.018	0.099	0.048	2.070	0.039	Supported
PSO x ATT -> INT	H_7	0.005	-0.047	0.040	1.187	0.235	Not-Supported

The study also examined the moderation effects of economic considerations through price saving orientation and immediacy concern through instant gratification orientation on the relationship between attitude towards Q-commerce and intention to adopt Q-commerce. The moderation results are shown in Table 5. The moderating effect of instant gratification orientation \times attitude on behavioural intention was positive and significant ($\beta = 0.099$, $t = 2.070$, $p = 0.039$), supporting H_6 . This result suggests that attitude towards Q-commerce adoption is more likely to translate into intention to adopt Q-commerce amongst those individuals who have high preference for instant delivery or immediate fulfilment. This finding supports prior literature on consumer psychology which posits that concern for immediate rewards influences purchase intention positively (Loewenstein, 1996; Dholakia, 2000). Contrary to this, the moderating effect of price-saving

orientation × attitude on behavioural intention was negative but statistically non-significant ($\beta = -0.047, t = 1.187, p = 0.235$). Thus, the result did not support H7. This indicates that concern of monetary saving does not significantly influence the relationship between attitude and intention, suggesting that convenience, time saving and preference for immediate fulfilment may outweigh concern for monetary savings in this format of online retail. Additionally, the direct effect of instant gratification orientation on intention to adopt Q-commerce was non-significant ($\beta = 0.016, p = 0.761$), suggesting that its primary role that of a moderator rather than direct effect.

Table 5b: Structural model results and hypothesis testing

Mediating Relationship	β	SD	T statistics	P values	Result
CON -> ATT -> INT	0.144	0.039	3.743	0.000	Supported
PBC -> ATT -> INT	0.114	0.032	3.513	0.000	Supported
TSO -> ATT -> INT	0.147	0.043	3.393	0.001	Supported

Specific indirect effects were examined to evaluate the role of attitude as the mediator. Findings reveal that all the three predictors of attitude, i.e., convenience, time saving orientation and perceived behavioural control significantly influence intention to adopt Q-commerce through attitude. Mediation analysis results are shown in Table 5b. These results indicate that attitude serves as a key explanatory mechanism through which utilitarian and control perceptions translate into intention to adopt Q-commerce. Further, Effect size (f^2) estimates indicate that attitude had the strongest influence on intention to adopt Q-commerce ($f^2 = 0.372$). Other predictors demonstrated minor but meaningful contributions. Predictive relevance was assessed using Stone–Geisser’s Q^2 values. The Q^2 values for attitude (0.429) and behavioral intention (0.451) were positive, confirming the model’s predictive relevance (Hair et al., 2022).

Figure 2: Structural Model (Source: SmartPLS 4.0)

6. DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The present study examined the adoption of Q-commerce in India through the theoretical lens of Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991), integrating utilitarian and psychological drivers. Supporting hypotheses H₁ and H₂, the significant influence of convenience and time saving suggested that reduction of effort and speed of delivery remains the core foundation of Q-commerce in India (Berry et al., 2002; Jiang et al., 2013). Similarly, supporting hypotheses H₃ and H₄, significant influence of perceived behavioural control over attitude towards Q-commerce and intention to adopt Q-commerce suggested that consumers' ease with Q-commerce apps and confidence in doing online payments play a vital role in forming a favourable attitude and intention towards Q-commerce adoption. This reinforces literature emphasizing role of control perception in technology adoption (Ajzen, 1991; Bosnjak et al., 2020).

Supporting hypothesis H₅, attitude was the strongest predictor of intention, emphasizing the role of evaluative constructs in emerging retail formats. Instant gratification orientation significantly moderated the relationship between attitude and intention, in the Q-commerce, adoption, supporting hypothesis H₆, while price saving orientation failed to moderate the same relationship, not supporting hypothesis H₇. This suggested that while preference for immediate fulfilment supports the translation of favourable attitude towards Q-commerce into intention to adopt Q-commerce, orientation for monetary rewards (discounts and cashbacks) does not do so.

Theoretically, the study contributes in three ways. Firstly, the study refines TPB in an emerging context of Q-commerce. Secondly, it demonstrates that utilitarian drivers like convenience and time saving (speed) can strengthen TPB. Thirdly, the study introduces immediate gratification as a boundary condition demonstrating how modern retail is shaped by consumers' preference for immediate fulfilment.

Practically, the study offers critical and actionable insights for Q-commerce platform managers. Firstly, managers should ensure seamless app design, frictionless convenience and reliable ultra-fast delivery. Marketing communication and promotion for Q-commerce should emphasize less on discounts and savings; rather, more emphasis should be given to instant delivery and time saving. Finally, loyalty programs may be offered to target the consumers who value immediacy in order to generate stronger repurchase intentions for using Q-commerce.

7. LIMITATIONS, FUTURE RESEARCH AND CONCLUSION

Despite its contributions, the study has certain limitations. Firstly, the study follows a cross-sectional design of data collection, limiting causality. Secondly, data for the study was collected from metropolitan cities only where the Q-commerce operations are highly active. This limits generalizability of the findings to tier-2 and tier-3 cities where Q-commerce has now expanded, but adoption conditions may differ. Third limitation is that the study focused on examining behavioural intention to adopt Q-commerce rather than actual usage behaviour, which would have been more insightful. Finally, despite the precautions, self-reporting nature of data collection might be subject to bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

The future research may focus on conducting studies on longitudinal data to observe the behaviour of the consumers related to Q-commerce over a period of time. Secondly, Q-commerce adoption in tier-2 and tier-3 cities may be studied to generate deeper insights in this emerging domain. Based

on city tier, geographical comparison analyses may be conducted with emphasis on adoption of Q-commerce. Thirdly, future studies may focus on actual consumer behaviour on Q-commerce based on primary or secondary (company) data. From the point of view of the constructs, the framework of the present study may be extended in future by incorporating constructs related to privacy concerns, platform trust, impulse purchase tendency and post purchase experience. This will enrich the present framework. Additionally, mixed-method or experimental designs may be adopted in future studies to establish causality between variables and further uncover the insights behind immediacy-driven consumption.

To conclude, Q-commerce presents a new retail avenue where speed, convenience and digital seamlessness reshape consumer expectations. The present study shows that the adoption intentions are driven by positive and favourable attitude, convenience, speed and behavioural control attributes. While instant gratification may help in translation of positive attitude into Q-commerce adoption intention, price saving considerations not necessarily do the same. Overall, the study demonstrated that adoption of Q-commerce is not just a technological choice but also a behavioural phenomenon where convenience and desire for immediate demand fulfilment play a vital role.

References

- 1) Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- 2) Al Ghamdi, R., Nguyen, A., & Jones, V. (2013). A study of influential factors in the adoption and diffusion of B2C e-commerce. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 4(1), 89–94.
- 3) Al-Mu'ani, L., Al-Momani, M. M., Amayreh, A., Aladwan, S. I., & Al-Rahmi, W. M. (2024). The effect of logistics and policy service quality on customer trust, satisfaction, and loyalty in quick commerce: A multigroup analysis of generation Y and generation Z. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 12 (3), 1417–1432. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2024.4.009>
- 4) ANI (2025, January 7). Quick commerce to expand into new categories and cities in 2025; smaller cities embrace the model: Bernstein report. *The Economic Times* <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/technology/quick-commerce-to-expand-into-new-categories-and-cities-in-2025-smaller-cities-embrace-the-model-bernstein-report/articleshow/117009974.cms?from=mdr>
- 5) Anonymous (2024, June 22). Could India Become a Quick Commerce Success Story? *Market Brew* <https://www.marketbrew.in/weekly-insights/growing-quick-commerce-india>
- 6) Berry, L. L., Seiders, K., & Grewal, D. (2002). Understanding service convenience. *Journal of Marketing*, 66(3), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.66.3.1.18505>
- 7) Bhatnagar K (2024, July 25). India's Q Commerce Ascent: A new Era in Shopping. *Redseer Strategy Consultants*. <https://redseer.com/newsletters/indias-q-commerce-ascent-a-new-era-inshopping>

- 8) Bosnjak, M., Ajzen, I., & Schmidt, P. (2020). The theory of planned behavior: Selected recent advances and applications. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 16(3), 352–356. <https://doi.org/10.5964/ejop.v16i3.3107>
- 9) Chavhan, R., & Dutta, P. (2025). Redesigning quick commerce fresh and short food supply chains: Circular economy strategies for sustainable last-mile operations. *British Food Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-05-2024-0560>
- 10) Deepthi, & Bansal, R. (2023). Employing TAM model to investigate the factors influencing quick commerce applications adoption using structural equation modeling technique. *International Journal of Mobile and Enterprise Design*. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMED.2023.134670>
- 11) Dholakia, U. M. (2000). Temptation and resistance: An integrated model of consumption impulse formation and enactment. *Psychology & Marketing*, 17(11), 955–982. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1520-6793\(200011\)17:11<955::AID-MAR3>3.0.CO;2-J](https://doi.org/10.1002/1520-6793(200011)17:11<955::AID-MAR3>3.0.CO;2-J)
- 12) Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224378101800104>
- 13) George, J. F. (2004). The theory of planned behavior and Internet purchasing. *Internet Research*, 14(3), 198–212. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10662240410542634>
- 14) Giang, N. T. P., Duy, N. B. P., Phat, N. T., Thao, D. T., & Tan, T. D. (2025). Investigating the Determinants of Repeat Purchase Intentions for One Commune One Products in Digital Platforms. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 15(5), 255.
- 15) Guru, S., Verma, S., Baheti, P., & Dagar, V. (2023). Assessing the feasibility of hyperlocal delivery model as an effective distribution channel. *Management Decision*, 61(6), 1634–1655. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-03-2022-0407>
- 16) Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2022). *Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using R: A workbook*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80519-7>
- 17) Harter, A., Stich, L., & Spann, M. (2025). The effect of delivery time on repurchase behavior in quick commerce. *Journal of Service Research*, 28(2), 211–227. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10946705241236961>
- 18) Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43, 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
- 19) Jiang, L., Yang, Z., & Jun, M. (2013). Measuring consumer perceptions of online shopping convenience. *Journal of Service Management*, 24(2), 191–214. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09564231311323962>
- 20) Kapoor, R., et al. (2023). Exploring quick commerce service experience: A moderated mediated investigation using SEM and fsQ-COMMERCEA. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2023.2213653>

- 21) Konuş, U., Verhoef, P. C., & Neslin, S. A. (2008). Multichannel shopper segments and their covariates. *Journal of Retailing*, 84(4), 398–413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2008.09.002>
- 22) Lee, T., Han, S. R., & Song, B. D. (2023). Optimization of OmniChannel distribution network using micro fulfillment center under demand uncertainty. *IEEE Access*, 11, 107496-107510. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3317690>
- 23) Lichtenstein, D. R., Ridgway, N. M., & Netemeyer, R. G. (1993). Price perceptions and consumer shopping behavior. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 30(2), 234–245. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224379303000208>
- 24) Loewenstein, G. (1996). Out of control: Visceral influences on behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 65(3), 272–292. <https://doi.org/10.1006/obhd.1996.0028>
- 25) Ma, H., Tsang, Y. P., & Lee, C. K. M. (2025). Optimizing multi-objective instant logistics with trucks and drones for the quick commerce order fulfilment. *Journal of Industrial and Production Engineering*, 42(5), 516-532. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21681015.2025.2468201>
- 26) Mischel, W., Shoda, Y., & Rodriguez, M. L. (1989). Delay of gratification in children. *Science*, 244(4907), 933–938. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.2658056>
- 27) NDTV (2025). In This Economy: 10 Minutes Or Bust — The Dark Side Of Fast Groceries. Retrieved from: <https://www.ndtvprofit.com/opinion/in-this-economy-10-minutes-or-bust-the-dark-side-of-fast-groceries>
- 28) Pachayappan, R. (2023). Multiple drone routing problem for on-demand hyperlocal market. *Transportation Research Record*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03611981221103872>
- 29) Pavlou, P. A., & Fygenson, M. (2006). Understanding and predicting electronic commerce adoption: An extension of the theory of planned behavior. *MIS Quarterly*, 30(1), 115–143. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25148720>
- 30) Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J.-Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavioral research: A critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 879–903. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.88.5.879>
- 31) Rai, H. B., Mariquivoi, J., Schorung, M., & Dablanc, L. (2023). Dark stores in the City of Light: Geographical and transportation impacts of ‘quick commerce’ in Paris. *Research in Transportation Economics*, 100, 101333.
- 32) Raj, G., Roy, D., de Koster, R., & Bansal, V. (2024). Stochastic modeling of integrated order fulfillment processes with delivery time promise: Order picking, batching, and last-mile delivery. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 316(3), 1114-1128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2024.03.003>
- 33) Sahu, A. K., Khan, M. Z., & Gupta, P. (2025). Instant food on your table: The role of logistics service quality dimensions in the adoption of instant online food delivery services. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 200, 104205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2025.104205>

- 34) Sanghi, N., Chandra Balodi, K., & Gupta, V. (2024). The emergence of the Indian hyperlocal grocery delivery industry: Dunzo v/s Blinkit. *Journal of Information Technology Teaching Cases*, 14(1), 119-128. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20438869231151449>
- 35) Seiders, K., Voss, G. B., Godfrey, A. L., & Grewal, D. (2007). SERVCON: Development and validation of a multidimensional service convenience scale. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 35, 144–156. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-006-0001-5>
- 36) Statista (2024, July). Quick Commerce-India. <https://www.statista.com/outlook/emo/online-food-delivery/grocery-delivery/quick-commerce/india>
- 37) Taylor, S., & Todd, P. A. (1995). Understanding information technology usage: A test of competing models. *Information Systems Research*, 6(2), 144–176. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.6.2.144>
- 38) Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425–478. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30036540>
- 39) Wakefield, K. L., & Inman, J. J. (2003). Situational price sensitivity. *Journal of Retailing*, 79(4), 199–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2003.09.004>
- 40) Yang, X., Ostermeier, M., & Hübner, A. (2024). Winning the race to customers with micro-fulfillment centers: an approach for network planning in quick commerce. *Central European Journal of Ops. Research*, 32(2), 295-334. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10100-023-00893-x>